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Risk-based control of *Campylobacter* spp. in broiler farms and slaughtered flocks to mitigate risk of human campylobacteriosis – A One Health approach

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ABSTRACT

Effects of risk-based control of *Campylobacter* spp. in Danish broiler farms and flocks were simulated, to assess potential reductions of human risk of campylobacteriosis, associated to the consumption of poultry meat produced in Denmark. Two national data streams were used and represented: Flock status by testing cloacal swabs (CS, 2018–2019) and carcass status by testing leg skin samples (LS, 2019). In the CS surveillance component all flocks slaughtered at the two major Danish slaughterhouses were tested with a polymerase chain reaction (PCR), while in LS one third randomly selected flocks were tested by culture (results in colony forming units per gram, cfu/g). Each farm was identified by its Central Husbandry Register (CHR) number. Two risk farm classification strategies (I-II) were based on CS data from 2018. Farms were classified as: always negative (Neg-CHRs), low risk (LowR-CHRs) and high risk (HighR-CHRs) farms. In strategy I, HighR-CHRs had more than five positive flocks, while in strategy II; they had more than 27.8% of the slaughtered flocks positive. Those two cut-offs were the annual 3rd quartiles across positive farms. Thereafter, a risk assessment model was used to estimate the annual relative risk (RR) of human campylobacteriosis in 2019, compared to that of 2013. Three hypothetical levels of cfu/g reductions (A, B and C) were simulated on the LS positive flocks (> 10 cfu/g) slaughtered by HighR-CHRs and were pairwise combined with the two classification strategies, yielding six risk-mitigation scenarios (A I-II; B I-II; C I-II). In scenarios A I-II, zero cfu/g were simulated, while in scenarios B and C, the original cfu/g were divided by three and by two. For each scenario, RRs were compared to the RR of the original cfu/g (scenario O).

In 2018, if all flocks from HighR-CHRs had been negative, the annual CS flock prevalence would have reduced from 19.7% to 7.6% (strategy I) or 9.6% (strategy II). Whereas in 2019, it would have reduced from 17.1% to 7.8% or 11.6%. In both years, HighR-CHRs delivered a high percentage of the total annual positive flocks (61.4–54.4% under strategy I and 51.2–32.6% with strategy II). In 2019, if HighR-CHRs had delivered only LS negative flocks, the RR would have reduced from 0.94 (scenario “O”) to 0.51 (A-I). Other scenarios showed smaller RR reductions. Targeting high risk farms/flocks for intensive control could improve One Health-ness of national action plans against *Campylobacter* spp.

1. Introduction

In Europe, campylobacteriosis is the most commonly reported foodborne zoonosis. It is caused by *Campylobacter* spp. and poultry meat is considered to be the most important source of human cases (EFSA European Food Safety Authority and ECDC European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2016), although infection has also been linked to consumption of other contaminated food or drink, occupational exposure, environmental and behavioural factors (e.g. water contact) (Patrick et al., 2004; Kuhn et al., 2020).

In Denmark, a National Action Plan aims to control *Campylobacter* spp. along the poultry meat food chain and carries out surveillance at different points between “farm” and “patients”. Human infections are notifiable and laboratories must notify confirmed cases to the national public health authority through the national microbiology database (Anonymous, 2019; Kuhn et al., 2020). The change of prevalence shows seasonality and usually peaks in summer months in both chickens and humans (Wedderkopp et al., 2000, 2001; Patrick et al., 2004; Kuhn et al., 2020).

Two main national data streams are collected for surveillance of

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Campylobacter spp. in broiler farms and meat. The presence of the pathogen in broiler farms is monitored by testing cloacal swabs (CS) of all slaughtered flocks at entry to the slaughterhouse, whereas the level of contamination on chilled carcasses (ready for retail) is monitored by testing randomly selected leg skin (LS) samples from approximately one third of the annually slaughtered flocks.

For years 2018–2021, the main target of the National Action Plan is to maintain low ($\leq 17.3\%$) CS flock prevalence combined for both conventional and organic farms. Nevertheless, the prevalence increased from 16.6% in 2017 to 24.6% in 2018, while the number of human registered cases was 4257 and 4546 respectively (Anonymous, 2019); and is expected to increase in the future (Kuhn et al., 2020). Thus, new methods of *Campylobacter* spp. control along the food chain are needed, to mitigate the risk of human disease (campylobacteriosis).

Cost-effectiveness of national disease control programs can be optimized by approaches of risk-based surveillance, where resources are prioritized towards population strata at higher risk of: being exposed, infected, affected, transmit infection or cause other consequences (Stärk et al., 2006; Alban et al., 2012; Hansen et al., 2018; Alban et al., 2020). Similarly, control actions can be more efficient to mitigate risk of disease such as foodborne diseases in humans, if targeted towards the populations of farms, animals, food products etc., which are more likely to carry the hazard of interest. Thus risk-based surveillance and (eventual) control actions can be set according to differential risk levels across different strata of the population of interest. Such risk levels can be defined using national data and applying objective procedures of risk assessment and statistical analysis (Alban et al., 2012; van Asselt et al., 2012; Alban et al., 2020). Approaches of risk-based control could be considered within the Danish Action plan. At the same time, the concept of “One Health (OH)” is also applicable, because collaborative efforts aimed at improving health, exist between at least two sectors (Bordier et al., 2020), namely the human health, the animal health, and the food safety sectors.

The aim of this study was to consider the Danish Action Plan as a One Health system and to investigate potential reductions in the risk of human campylobacteriosis, by simulating effects of risk-based control of prevalence and contamination in high-risk farms and flocks, which were identified integrating surveillance information from different data streams and years.

2. Materials and methods

Data from the Danish CS (2018–2019) and LS (2019) surveillance components were used. In both datasets, the identification number registered in the Central Husbandry Register (CHR) represented each farm. In the CS data, the farm type was defined e.g. as “organic broiler” (Virksomhedsart = Økologiske Slagtekyllinger) or simply “broiler” (Slagtekyllinger), while in the LS data a specific project number was used for conventional, free range or organic farms. For this study, we focused on the conventional farms, since they represent most of the Danish poultry population. Accordingly, the data regarded 3012 and 3004 flocks tested in CS during 2018 and 2019 (respectively); plus 1248 flocks tested in LS in the latter year.

In the CS surveillance component, every slaughtered flock was tested by a pool of 12 cloacal swabs, with sampling of two broilers per swab, analyzed by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) (Lund et al., 2004). Results were recorded as “positive” or “negative”.

In the LS component, one leg skin sample (from each randomly selected flock) was tested by culture, according to (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis, 2007; Rosenquist et al., 2007). Results were provided in colony forming units per gram (cfu/g) and flocks with ≥ 10 cfu/g were classified LS positive and otherwise negative.

2.1. Application of One Health concepts and risk-based control within the study

In this study, the two surveillance components CS and LS, were considered as belonging to the same One Health surveillance system, although they gave information on presence of *Campylobacter* spp. at two different levels: farm or pre-harvest (CS) and meat or post-harvest (LS) levels, respectively. These data streams were integrated to assess potential reductions of human campylobacteriosis, associated to the consumption of broiler meat produced in Denmark. A previously published risk assessment model (Teunis and Havelaar, 2000; Nauta et al., 2008), which can be used to assess risk of human campylobacteriosis, represented the public health sector.

The principles of risk-based surveillance and control described in the introduction (Stärk et al., 2006; Alban et al., 2012; van Asselt et al., 2012; Alban et al., 2020), were applied through three steps:

- 1 Danish conventional broiler farms were classified into three different risk strata (always negative = Neg-CHRs, low risk = LowR-CHRs, and high risk = HighR-CHRs), using CS testing results from 2018, and according to two risk-based classification strategies I-II, (Section 2.2).
- 2 Within each risk-stratum, CHRs which were CS tested in 2018, were matched with their LS testing results from 2019 (Section 2.3), and
- 3 For the HighR-CHRs identified in step 1, alternative meat contamination levels were simulated in their 2019 LS positive flocks identified in step 2 (Section 2.4).

Accordingly, step 1 was carried out to identify the stratum (of farms) at higher risk of delivering infected flocks, where control actions (and/or additional surveillance) could be prioritized to optimize cost-effectiveness of *Campylobacter* spp. control along the food chain.

In step 2, it was evaluated if prevalence and levels of meat contamination, differed between flocks slaughtered by farms categorized into the different risk strata (step 1).

Finally, in step 3, the potential effect of eventual control actions at pre and/or at post-harvest levels, was simulated by reducing the original meat contamination levels observed in LS positive flocks delivered by HighR-CHRs in 2019.

2.2. Step 1: risk-based classification of farms and flocks according to CS testing in 2018

The CS data stream was used to generate the risk classification of farms, because this surveillance component was a census that tested all flocks slaughtered at the two major Danish slaughterhouses, which slaughter most of the Danish broiler flocks.

Farms were divided into Neg-CHRs, LowR-CHRs, HighR-CHRs based on the annual number or percentage of positive flocks they slaughtered during 2018.

The risk-based classification strategy I, was based on the annual number of positive flocks delivered for slaughter. This strategy was considered because it was assumed that, the higher the number of positive flocks delivered by a farm, the higher the risk posed for humans. Farms were classified as HighR-CHRs, if they delivered more than five positive flocks a year. This was above the national 3rd quartile across all farms with at least one CS positive flock.

The risk-based classification strategy II was based on the annual percentage of positive flocks delivered for slaughter. Thus, in that case, the possibility of being classified as HighR-CHR took into account for both the number of positive flocks and the total number of slaughtered flocks per farm. Accordingly, in this strategy, the risk categorization reflected the within-farm annual incidence of slaughtered positive flocks. Farms were classified as HighR-CHRs, if in 2018, they delivered more than 27.8% of their flocks as positive. Also in this case, the cut-off was the national 3rd quartile across all CS positive farms.

2.3. Step 2: combining CS risk-strata 2018 with their LS results 2019

Data handling and analysis were carried out using the free software R (R Core Team, 2013). Descriptive statistics were carried out at both farm and flock levels, considering annual and monthly surveillance periods.

Because the LS component was a survey design derived by random sampling, not all flocks tested in CS were also culture tested. During 2018, approximately one third of the slaughtered flocks tested in the CS component were also tested in the LS component.

Since we wanted to evaluate, whether CS data from previous year could be used to predict farms (and flocks) at higher risk of being positive in the following year, in any of the two components, the two data streams, CS 2018 and LS 2019, were collated by merging on CHRs.

The prevalence of positive flocks was estimated at national level. Thereafter, the proportion of HighR-CHR and of their flocks (out of the total tested and out of the total positives) was calculated. For the merged CHRs, the distribution of cfu/g observed in the LS positive flocks was compared between risk-strata, under each risk-based classification strategy (I or II).

2.4. Step 3: impact of risk-based control scenarios on annual risk of human campylobacteriosis

An existing risk assessment model (Teunis and Havelaar, 2000; Nauta et al., 2008), was used to assess the potential impact of eventual control measures targeted to HighR-CHR and their flocks, on risk of human campylobacteriosis.

The risk assessment model relates the probability of illness following the consumption of a meal prepared with chicken meat, to the *Campylobacter* concentration found on the leg skin. It relates the measured leg skin concentration, with the concentration on the chicken meat. It combines a consumer phase model describing the transfer, the survival of *Campylobacter* during food preparation and the subsequent exposure to the consumer (Nauta et al., 2008) with a dose response model (Teunis and Havelaar, 2000). It has previously been used by (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011; Koutsoumanis et al., 2020) and by Nauta et al. (2012). The mathematical details can be found in these papers.

Since 2014, the model has been run annually to estimate the public health risk of human campylobacteriosis associated to broiler meat produced in Denmark, relative (RR) to 2013. It is informed with concentrations (cfu/g) of *Campylobacter* spp. detected through the LS component, in flocks slaughtered at the two major Danish slaughterhouses. In 2019, 998 out of 1248 conventional flocks tested in LS, were slaughtered at those slaughterhouses (495 and 503 flocks, respectively). The remaining 250 LS tested flocks were slaughtered at a third slaughterhouse, which was not yet opened when the baseline risk level was defined in 2013. Thus, culture results from those 250 flocks were not used in the risk assessment model, in line with the annual model runs, which are carried out to inform changes of RR within the National *Campylobacter* Action Plan (Mette Rørbæk Gantzhorn, Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, personal communication).

Three hypothetical levels of reduction (A, B and C) in the concentration (cfu/g) of *Campylobacter* spp., were simulated for the LS positive flocks slaughtered by HighR-CHR:

- A Concentrations reduced by 100% (i.e. original cfu/g reduced to 0)
- B Concentrations reduced by 66% (i.e. original cfu/g divided by three).
- C Concentrations reduced by 50% (i.e. original cfu/g divided by two).

Thereafter, the three levels of cfu/g reduction, were pairwise combined with the two farms risk-based classification strategies (I and II), yielding a total of six simulated risk-mitigation scenarios: A-I and A-II, B-I and B-II, C-I and C-II. Thus, scenarios A (I-II) simulated full control-success in the high risk stratum, while scenarios B and C simulated more modest control in the same stratum.

The RR estimates obtained under each simulated scenario were

compared to the RR estimated in the original contamination scenario "O", where the original concentration of *Campylobacter* spp. was used for all farms.

3. Results

3.1. Contribution of HighR-CHR to national farm prevalence

In 2018, 160 conventional farms (CHR) were tested in the CS surveillance component and 125 (78.1%) of these delivered at least one positive flock for slaughter. The remaining 35 farms (21.9%) were always negative (Neg-CHR).

In strategy I, 29 farms were classified as HighR-CHR, corresponding to 18.1% of the tested and 23.2% of the positive farms. In 2019, the HighR-CHR classified on the 2018 data, represented 16.2% of the tested and 20.9% of the positives.

In strategy II, 31 farms were classified as HighR-CHR, corresponding to 19.4% of the tested and 24.8% of the positive farms. In 2019, the HighR-CHR classified on 2018 data, represented 15.6% of the tested and 19.1% of the positives.

During 2018, the median monthly percentage of positive farms classified as HighR-CHR was around 55.0% for both strategies. HighR-CHR constituted most ($\geq 50.0\%$) of the positive farms in almost all months. The only exceptions occurred during summer (June, July and August), in October (strategy I) or November (strategy II) (Fig. 1).

3.2. Contribution from HighR-CHR to national flock prevalence

In 2018, 19.7% (594) of the CS tested conventional flocks were positive. If all flocks from HighR-CHR had been negative, the flock prevalence would have been $19.7-12.1\% = 7.6\%$ (strategy I), or $19.7-10.1\% = 9.6\%$ (strategy II).

In 2019, 17.1% (515) of the tested flocks were positive. This prevalence would have been 7.8% (strategy I) or 11.6% (strategy II), if all flocks from HighR-CHR classified on the 2018 data, had been negative.

In strategy I, the HighR-CHR delivered 33.2% of the flocks tested in 2018 and 30.5% of those tested in 2019. Moreover, HighR-CHR delivered 61.4% and 54.4% of the positive flocks in 2018 and 2019, respectively.

In strategy II, HighR-CHR delivered 19.6% and 17.1% of all flocks in 2018 and 2019, and of the positive flocks: 51.2% and 32.6%, respectively.

During 2018, the median monthly percentage of positive flocks slaughtered by HighR-CHR was 68.3% for strategy I and 63.6% for strategy II. Under both strategies, HighR-CHR delivered most ($> 50.0\%$) of the monthly positive flocks. The only exceptions occurred in July and August with strategy I, and in July-August-November for strategy II (Fig. 2).

3.3. Descriptive statistics on matching between surveillance components and years

The CHR tested in CS during 2018 and matched with LS data from 2019, delivered 79.4% (991/1248) of the total LS tested flocks and 63.9% (260/407) of the LS positive flocks. The remaining 20.6% (257/1248) of the LS tested flocks were slaughtered by farms that were not tested in CS in 2018 (e.g. because not open yet), or were slaughtered at the new abattoir (i.e. disregarded as explained in Section 2.4). Under both testing strategies, LowR-CHR represented the biggest group of matched farms, followed by the HighR-CHR and Neg-CHR. For 59.4% (95/160) of the farms tested in CS during 2018, at least one LS positive result was found in 2019 (Table 1).

3.4. Carcass contamination in the different risk strata

In 2019, 407 out of 1248 (32.6%) LS samples were positive. If LS

Fig. 1. Monthly number of Danish conventional broiler farms *Campylobacter* positive in cloacal swabs (CS) during 2018, classified by risk-based classification strategy (I and II) into HighR-CHR = high-risk farms and LowR-CHR= low risk farms.

Fig. 2. Monthly number of flocks found *Campylobacter* positive in cloacal swabs (CS) during 2018 and delivered by Danish conventional broiler farms classified by risk-based classification strategy (I and II) into HighR-CHR = high-risk farms or LowR-CHR= low-risk farms.

Table 1

Danish conventional broiler farms tested for *Campylobacter* in cloacal swabs (CS) during 2018, matched with their leg skin (LS) positive flocks detected in 2019. Results presented by risk-based classification strategy (I- II) and farms risk strata defined using the mentioned CS data. Neg-CHRs = farms that delivered only negative flocks. LowR-CHRs = Low risk farms that delivered ≤ 5 positive flocks (strategy I) or had ≤ 27.8% of the slaughtered flocks positive (strategy II). HighR-CHRs = high risk farms that delivered > 5 positive flocks (strategy I) or had > 27.8% of their slaughtered flocks positive (strategy II).

Matched farms	Neg-CHRs	LowR-CHRs	HighR-CHRs
Strategy I	17	56	22
Strategy II	17	60	18
LS positive flocks	Neg-CHRs	LowR-CHRs	HighR-CHRs
Strategy I	40	115	105
Strategy II	40	161	59

positive flocks delivered by (matched) HighR-CHRs had been always negative at the culture test, the mentioned LS flock prevalence would have been reduced to $(407-105)/1248 = 24.2\%$ or $(407-59)/1248 = 27.9\%$ under strategy I or II, respectively.

For both strategies, LS positive flocks slaughtered by the Neg-CHRs (Table 2) had a median contamination of 330 cfu/g (2.5 log-10). In strategy I, LS positive flocks slaughtered by LowR-CHRs had the same median cfu/g, while those from HighR-CHRs had a median 1.5 times higher (1.1 times higher if considering the corresponding log-10 values). Thus, flocks delivered by HighR-CHRs showed higher contamination levels than flocks delivered by other farms.

In strategy II, LS positive flocks slaughtered by LowR-CHRs had median contamination 1.3 times higher than that of Neg-CHRs, while those slaughtered by HighR-CHRs had median 1.2 times higher. Hence, with that classification strategy, flocks delivered by LowR-CHRs appeared those with the highest contamination.

Table 2

Distribution of colony forming units per gram (cfu/g), found on *Campylobacter* positive leg skin (LS) samples (one sample per tested flock) during 2019, in Danish conventional broiler farms classified into the high (HighR-CHRs), low (LowR-CHRs) and negative (Neg-CHRs) risk strata. Results are presented under risk-based classification I (> 5 annual positive flocks) and II (> 27.8% of annually slaughtered flocks positive), according to testing in the cloacal swabs (CS) component during 2018. Within brackets are the log-10 transformed values approximated to the first decimal.

I, distribution cfu/g	Min	1st Q.	Median	Mean	3rd Q.	Max
Neg-CHRs	10 (1.0)	48 (1.7)	330 (2.5)	638 (2.4)	823 (2.9)	3400 (3.5)
LowR-CHRs	10 (1.0)	30 (1.5)	330 (2.5)	1091 (2.4)	1250 (3.1)	16,000 (4.2)
HighR-CHRs	10 (1.0)	110 (2.0)	500 (2.7)	1484 (2.6)	1800 (3.3)	10,000 (4.0)
II, distribution cfu/g	Min	1st Q.	Median	Mean	3rd Q.	Max
Neg-CHRs	10 (1.0)	48 (1.7)	330 (2.5)	638 (2.3)	823 (2.9)	3400 (3.5)
LowR-CHRs	10 (1.0)	40 (1.6)	440 (2.6)	1300 (2.5)	1600 (3.2)	16,000 (4.2)
HighR-CHRs	10 (1.0)	120 (2.1)	390 (2.6)	1221 (2.6)	1500 (3.2)	10,000 (4.0)

3.5. Effects of risk mitigation scenarios

The effect of the different risk mitigation scenarios on the estimated human health risk is presented in Fig. 3. All scenarios used the original RR estimates obtained from the risk assessment model for years 2014 to 2019, compared to baseline year 2013. For 2019, the original

contamination scenario (O) had RR = 0.94 (Fig. 3, black line).

Under strategy I, this RR decreased to 0.51 when the HighR-CHR only delivered LS negative flocks (A-I); to 0.75 when they reduced the contamination to one third (B-I) and to 0.81 with half reduction (C-I) (Fig. 3, red lines).

Under strategy II, where HighR-CHRs were classified by their annual percentage of positive flocks (instead of number), the risk-based control plan had less influence on human health risk and the reduced RR values were 0.74 (A-II), 0.85 (B-II) and 0.88 (C-II) (Fig. 3, blue lines).

4. Discussion

This study demonstrates the true One Health concept, where risk mitigation in the animal health sector, can be measured in the food safety sector and has demonstrational impact for the public health sector. It was shown that by using risk-based control, the risk of human campylobacteriosis could be reduced remarkably, compared to the non-risk-based control. If resources are available, eventual additional efforts of risk-based control (and/or surveillance) could be prioritized to approximately one fifth of the Danish farms and their flocks. This proof of concept is likely to benefit not only for the Danish Action Plan, but also in other countries and in other control programmes, where One Health approaches are needed.

4.1. Importance of One Health and risk-based control

The concept of One Health has become increasingly popular during the last decade (Bordier et al., 2020). Some advantage of applying this concept, within national programmes of zoonotic disease surveillance and control, is that surveillance information collected and collated

Fig. 3. Simulated annual risk of human campylobacteriosis associated to Danish broiler meat, relative (RR) to 2013. The risk assessment was based on colony forming unit per gram (cfu/g) detected in the leg skins (LS) of flocks slaughtered at the two major Danish slaughterhouses (998/1248 LS tested flocks) during 2019. RRs were estimated for pairwise combinations of risk-based farm classification strategy (I or II) with potential levels of reduction in cfu/g (A, B, and C), representing six alternative risk-mitigation scenarios (A I-II; B I-II; C I-II). In strategy I, during 2018, high risk farms (HighR-CHRs) slaughtered more than five flocks positive in cloacal swabs (CS), while in strategy II, HighR-CHRs had more than 27.8% of their slaughtered flocks CS positive. In scenario O, the original cfu/g were used for all LS positive flocks. In scenarios A (I-II), such contamination level was reduced to zero for all flocks of HighR-CHRs, while it was divided by three or by two in scenarios B (I-II) and C (I-II), respectively. N.B. for years 2013 to 2018, the RR did not change between scenarios because these were only studied for LS data 2019.

through different data streams (from different populations and sectors), can be interpreted and used at national level to benefit public health.

It is possible to determine the best place for control actions in the One Health continuum (animal health, food safety and public health), by looking across populations and integrating data from different surveillance components along the food chain. Especially for foodborne pathogens, this integrated risk-based approach, could facilitate optimized resource allocations and can improve cost-effectiveness of national programmes aimed at reducing the risk of infection/disease in humans.

This study showed how both concepts of One Health and risk-based control of disease, could be implemented with the Danish Action Plan against *Campylobacter* spp., to achieve in a cost-effective manner, the target of maintaining low prevalence of infection in farms and slaughtered flocks, as well as decreasing campylobacteriosis caused by chicken meat in humans.

4.2. Effects of risk-based stratification procedure

When risk-based surveillance and/or control is/are pursued, the target population is classified in risk-groups composed of different surveillance units, by pre-defined (risk) factors (Stärk et al., 2006; Alban et al., 2020), such as farms or flocks. In this study two strategies of risk-based classifications were used (I and II) and were based on information from national data. As observed by van Asselt et al. (2012), when statistical analysis is used for ranking companies, and when data can be made available from the national authority or from producers, then the methodology used to derive the various risk-based rankings can be properly grounded and documented, to improve transparency across sectors and stakeholders.

Positive farms were allocated into the highest risk stratum according to their annual number (strategy I) or annual percentage (strategy II) of positive flocks. Therefore, the stratification was based on quantitative descriptive analysis and assuming that the human health risk posed by each positive farm, was proportional to the annual number (or percentage) of positive flocks slaughtered. For both strategies, the national 3rd quartiles were used as cut-offs to distinguish the HighR-CHRs from the LowR-CHRs. In this way, objectivity between farms and consistency across years can be achieved. For example, if stratification strategy I had been applied also to CS data from 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2019; a similar proportion of farms would have been classified as HighR-CHRs.

Similar cut-offs (3rd quartiles = 3–5 positive flocks per positive farm) would have been obtained, and most of the HighR-CHRs spotted in 2018, would have been classified similarly in different years (results not shown).

The two risk-based stratification strategies categorized a similar number of farms (29 vs 31) into the high risk stratum. In both investigated years, the CS flock prevalence would have been reduced to approximately one third (strategy I) or half (strategy II), if all flocks delivered by HighR-CHRs had been negative.

In both strategies, during 2018, the HighR-CHRs delivered most of the monthly CS positive flocks. The main exceptions occurred during summer for strategy I and in summer-November for strategy II (Fig. 2). During summer, the flock prevalence and the incidence in humans are known to peak (Wedderkopp et al., 2000, 2001; Patrick et al., 2004; Kuhn et al., 2020). The reason for such exceptions could be that, especially during summer, farms that are usually negative deliver a few positive flocks. These would be LowR-CHRs.

At the same time, strategy I was able to predict a higher percentage of tested and positive flocks for the current (2018) and the following year (2019), because it was based on the number of positive flocks per positive farm. Thus, the probability of being classified as HighR-CHR was higher for positive large farms (producing several batches) than for positive small farms. It can be expected that reducing the positive flocks delivered from HighR-CHRs could reduce risk for humans, since the probability of human infection should be directly related to the number of delivered contaminated flocks and retailed meat packages. On the

other hand, this strategy could lead to complacency in *Campylobacter* control in smaller farms.

Strategy II provided a smaller reduction of public health risk (Section 4.4), and some of the farms classified as HighR-CHRs were actually small farms that delivered a small number of positive flocks, but which represented more than 27.8% of those they slaughtered. Then, for example, a farm delivering 4 positive flocks out of 8 would be classified HighR-CHR, as a farm with 8 positive flocks out of 16 slaughtered. In the second case (assuming similar cfu/g) the risk of human campylobacteriosis would be higher, despite the percentage of positive flocks delivered per farm being the same (50%). The importance of the concentration level (cfu/g) per positive flock is addressed below (Sections 4.3–4.4).

Strengths and limitations of both strategies should be considered if the risk-based control approach is used to improve the National Action Plan. Especially under stratification strategy I, “extra” efforts of surveillance and control would be prioritized towards a small proportion of farms, but delivering most of the positive flocks.

4.3. Predicted differences in LS contamination levels between risk-strata

The overlapping of interquartile ranges did not suggest statistically significant difference between cfu/g of LS positive flocks delivered by the different strata (Table 2).

Nevertheless, in strategy I, HighR-CHRs had a median cfu/g that was 1.5 times higher than that of Neg-CHRs and LowR-CHRs (Table 2). Thus, it could be expected that farms identified into the high-risk stratum by CS positivity, could deliver (even in the following year) LS positive flocks which are more contaminated than those slaughtered from other strata.

In strategy II, the LowR-CHRs showed the highest median cfu/g (Table 2), because some large farms which delivered several CS positive flocks, still fell below the threshold of 27.8% positive flocks and were classified as LowR-CHRs, increasing the median cfu/g of that group.

Therefore, strategy II seems less precise than strategy I, if the target is to predict the farms and flocks that are more likely to have the higher LS contamination levels in the following year. However, the actual effect of reducing concentration of *Campylobacter* spp. on meat is less certain than the effect of producing less positive flocks.

4.4. Relative risk reductions

From a general point of view, reductions of relative risk (RR) were more evident under strategy I than in strategy II. With the former, it appeared that the RR could have been almost halved (scenario A-I) if HighR-CHRs identified by CS testing in 2018, had always delivered LS negative flocks in 2019 (Fig. 3). Other combinations of risk classification strategy (I-II) and level of reduction of cfu/g (A, B and C) showed less impact on the RR values (Fig. 3).

When considering the two strategies under the same or different reductions of contamination levels (A or B or C); the RR decreases were more evident in strategy I than in strategy II. For example, under the same reduction level A (cfu/g reduced to zero in LS positive flocks delivered by HighR-CHRs), the RR was 0.51 in A-I and 0.75 in A-II (Fig. 3). A reduction of the relative risk (RR) of human campylobacteriosis due to fresh poultry meat by 50%, compared to the level in 2013, is the current target of the National Action Plan “Campylobacter in broilers 2018–2021” (Anonymous, 2019).

When comparing the two strategies under different levels of reduction in cfu/g, it can be noted that scenario B-I gave similar RR (0.75) of scenario A-II (0.74). This suggests that, reducing of 66% the contamination of LS positive flocks delivered by HighR-CHRs identified by strategy I, could reduce the risk of human campylobacteriosis similarly to the situation where all flocks delivered by HighR-CHRs identified by strategy II were completely negative (reduction in cfu/g = 100%). It is unlikely that all farms would be able to change from being HighR-CHR

to Neg-CHR in one year and reductions lower than 100% are probably more realistic. Thus, it could be expected that risk based control under strategy I, gives more noticeable effects on risk of human campylobacteriosis (within shorter time), compared to the situation where strategy II is used.

For both strategies, it is difficult to estimate the (exact) health impact of risk mitigation actions beforehand, since this could be variable depending on the level of control measures used along the food chain and would probably take more than one year. Nevertheless, this study provides an initial proof of concept for applying risk-based surveillance and control within the National Action Plan, and gives a general overview of the proportion of farms and flocks that could be prioritized for eventual (ad-hoc) measures of risk-mitigation and/or surveillance. Surveillance actors and stakeholders involved in the National Action Plan could decide which risk-based classification strategy to use. If the main target was the reduction of risk of infection for humans, then probably strategy I could be preferable. If “fairness” between farmers had to be prioritized, then strategy II could be used.

4.5. Limitations

In this study, the 3rd quartile number (or percentage) of positive flocks per positive farm were used as cut-offs to identify the HighR-CHRs. Other percentiles could be used (e.g. the 50th, 90th, 95th percentiles). The higher the percentile, the lower the number of farms classified as HighR-CHRs and the lower the effect on risk to consumers will be. In opposition, low cut-offs would lead to inclusion of more farms in the HighR-CHR stratum, diminishing the returns of efforts from the further farms, and drawing towards blanket control methods. The used cut-off should be a balance between the costs of direct surveillance-control actions needed and the eventual consequences of “errors” (e.g. human infections, production losses, trade loss, reputation loss etc.). A complete cost-benefit analysis was not carried out to compare the cost-efficiency of risk-based surveillance/control vs. the current (beginning-2021) system. Pilot studies could be used, to evaluate in practical terms the logistics of the proposed risk-based procedures and control actions, which can reduce meat contamination along the food chain.

In this study potential effects of risk-based control measures were simulated by reducing positivity and meat contamination levels in flocks slaughtered by high risk farms. Different interventions could be applied (or improved) to reduce flock prevalence and contamination. For example, at the farm level some interventions could be: improving biosecurity and hygiene, use of water and feed additives, discontinued thinning, employing few and well trained staff, etc. (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011; Koutsoumanis et al., 2020). At processing and post-harvest levels (i.e. at abattoir or retailing) official controls (like inspections), education (e.g. developing codes of practice) and advice (van Asselt et al., 2012), could be applied and microbiological criteria may be used (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011; Nauta et al., 2012)

Regarding the merging of datasets, not all CHR tested in CS in 2018 matched with the LS data 2019, because the LS component did not test all flocks slaughtered at the two major slaughterhouses and because the two datasets were collected in different years. Thus, the median cfu/g estimated for each risk stratum, as well as the simulated RRs were based only on the CHRs, which could be matched between data streams and years. It is likely that the impact of risk-based control actions could have resulted higher than we estimated, if more carcasses from HighR-CHRs (2018) had been tested in LS (2019). Furthermore, a reduction in the (non-direct) effect of cross-contamination in the slaughterhouse could also occur, if less positive flocks are delivered. Our analyses did not account for that kind of potential reduction, which may also add to the underestimated benefits, although previous quantitative microbial risk assessment studies suggested that cross-contaminated flocks do contribute little to the public health risk (Nauta et al., 2009; EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011).

Finally, it must be said that the number of positive broilers present in

a flock, could also affect the risk for humans, since more meat packages (i.e. food doses) could be obtained from larger infected flocks. Unfortunately, the flock size was not available in the data we used, and thus, it could not be included in the risk assessment model. If in the future, the number of slaughtered broilers is reported from the two surveillance components, then the relative contribution of each infected flock to the risk for humans could be assessed more precisely.

5. Conclusion

This study provides an initial proof of concept for possible improvements of the Danish Action Plan against *Campylobacter* spp., through application of the principles of One Health and risk-based control. Resources to survey and control *Campylobacter* spp. could be prioritized across years, towards broiler farms and flocks that can be predicted to be at higher risk of infection and posing higher risk for humans, according to surveillance data from previous year. Targeting the high-risk farms for control could provide a large reduction in campylobacteriosis risk to consumers. Additional cost-benefit analysis and pilot studies are suggested to further investigate the practicability and the impact of risk-based control at pre- and/or at post-harvest levels.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alessandro Foddai: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Maarten Nauta:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Johanne Ellis-Iversen:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declarations of Competing Interest

None.

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